

Developing An Automated Database for Cadastral Information

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Abstract

The traditional method of managing cadastral information using analogue systems presents several challenges, such as high maintenance costs, data redundancy, and a lack of spatial integration. This study explores the development of an automated cadastral information system using open-source tools like PostgreSQL, PostGIS, QGIS, and React.js. Mandate Housing Estate in Ilorin, Kwara State, serves as the case study for designing and implementing the spatial database and user interface. Attribute and geometric data were collected, structured, and integrated on a Heroku server. The resulting system supports spatial queries, improves land data access, and provides a template for scalable land management systems in Nigeria and beyond.

KEYWORDS: Cadastral Information System, PostgreSQL, PostGIS, QGIS, React.js, Database, GIS

Introduction

The most valuable resource on earth that supports human existence is widely acknowledged to be the Land. It supports the agricultural, residential, cultural, educational, and other activities for the main dominion over some portion of the earth (Musa, S. I., Shuaibu, M. A., Mshelia, A. D., and Amusuk, 2016); therefore, it can be said that Land is owned and managed by man. The Land is both a tangible good and an abstract idea because the rights to own or use it are just as much a part of the Land as the things that grow in its soil (Cetl & Tomi, 2011). Moreover, the Land is the foundation of most human activity and development initiatives. Therefore, a systematic record of land size, land purposes, land shape, location, and rights in Land is vital for public administration, planning, land development, and private transactions in Land.

Furthermore, reliable and efficient land data records are essential for effective resource management and environmental problem-solving. These emphasise the importance of keeping accurate records of land parcels and their uses (Wright et al., 1989). The Cadastre is a public catalogue arranged methodically and contains information on properties within a locality based on information from Cadastral Surveying Data (Henssen, 1995). From a database perspective, a cadastre is a land information system where information is referenced to unique, well-defined units of Land, generally referred to as land parcels. The outlines of these land parcels are usually shown on large-scale maps, are linked to textual land title registers, and provide a spatial reference for other spatial or a-spatial, parcel-related data. An efficient cadastre begins with creating and maintaining an up-to-date record of all land use purposes and interests in Land. Such as a register of land use, their boundary, and interest in Land to form a basis for a cadastre. Cadastre furnishes the public with spatial and attribute information about a parcel of

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Land. The primary objective of the Cadastre is to meet the needs of various users by providing information at the parcel level.

On the other hand, an information system may be formally defined as a combination of human and technical resources, together with a set of organizing procedures that produce information in support of certain managerial requirements (Dale et al., n.d.). The building block of the cadastral information system is a geometric description of land parcels, connected to other records that describe the nature of interests, ownership, or control over those interests, as well as the improvements to the property and its value. Additionally, the cadastral information system includes information like the purpose, size, shape, and location of individual parcels. The establishment of fully functional digital cadastral databases will help provide a proper information system that will facilitate Development in an ever-changing world of technology. Conceptually, for the Cadastral Information System, logical and physical models were constructed and utilized to improve the parcel and its value, creating the Cadastral Information System using an Entity-Relationship model.

Materials and Methods

The critical phases for automating cadastral information system design are discussed in this chapter, including the database design, equipment (instruments), materials, and procedures used in this study. During cadastral information system design automation, these phases are intended to be considered. The methodology is simple

- i. Data collection.
- ii. Data processing.
- iii. Data storage (hosting of the database in a server).
- iv. Development of a Graphics User Interface (GUI).

Database Design

An information system includes all resources within the organization involved in collecting, managing, using, and disseminating information. These resources in a computerized environment include the data itself, the database management system (DBMS) software, the hardware and storage media of the computer system, the personnel who use and manage the data (such as database administrators, end users, parametric users, and so on), the applications software that accesses and updates the data, and the application programmers who create these applications. (Elmasri and Navathe, 1994). Database design is one of the fundamental processes in every GIS work executed. It is a process by which real-world entities and their relationship are analyzed and modelled to solve specific problems and find a solution to questions of interest. The heart of a Geographic Information System is a well-structured, i.e., spatial database. The process of designing a database is called data modelling. Database design has some essential phases. These phases of the database design process are:

- i. Requirements Collection and Analysis: Identifying and analyzing the expectations of users and intended uses. These requirements are exposed by the analysis of existing documents.
- ii. Conceptual Database Design: Examines the requirements exposed in the first phase and produces a conceptual schema. In this schema, database objects and their behaviours are represented.
- iii. Choice of a DBMS: This step is governed by several factors, such as software acquisition cost, maintenance cost, hardware acquisition cost, database creation and conversion cost, personnel cost, training cost, and operating cost.
- iv. Data Model Mapping (Logical Database Design): In this phase, the conceptual model is mapped into the data model of the DBMS in two steps. A system- Data Model Mapping (Logical Database Design): In this phase, the conceptual model is mapped into the data model of the DBMS in two steps. A system-independent mapping is applied in the first step, and no specific characteristics or

exceptional cases of the DBMS are considered. In the second step, schemas are mapped into a particular DBMS. The schemas from the first step should be adjusted according to specific characteristics of the DBMS.

- v. Physical Database Design: selecting particular access paths and storage structures for database files to achieve optimal performance forms this phase. vi. Database System Implementation: After logical and physical designs have been completed, empty database files are created, and the data is loaded.

System Selection

A. Hardware components

- H.P. 1 T.B. Hard disk, Core i7 Intel processor, and H.P. 1 T.B. Intel Celeron processor.
- 12GB RAM size & 8GB RAM size
- 64-bit Windows 10 operating system
- 5 volts HP Optical Mouse (2)

B. Printer/Plotter

- HP LaserJet printer 47
- HP LaserJet A3 plotter

C. Software

The software used includes:

- QGIS 3.18.2 for the creation of layers, points, and polygons.
- PostgreSQL for data processing, manipulating, and analytical operations.
- PostGIS is an extension in the P.G. admin that adds geographic object support to the object-relational PostgreSQL database. Git Bash is an application for Microsoft Windows environments that provides an emulation layer for a Git command-line experience.
- Node.js is used for the design of traditional websites and backend API services. For example, it is used for hosting the database link and designing the graphical user interface.
- Heroku server is used for hosting the spatial and non-spatial data to be related in PostgreSQL.
- Microsoft Word 2016 for report typing and word processing.
- Microsoft Excel 2016 for editing and arranging the attribute data.

D. Personnel

- Leke John Oluwagbemiga (Student Surveyor)
- Sakariyah Abdurrahman (Student Surveyor)

3.7 Data Processing

Data processing describes the stages and processes of converting the acquired data into information. Data are organized into a structure, group, and database. The layout plan for the study area was obtained from the Office of the Surveyor-General, Ilorin, Kwara State. The layout was exported into QGIS 3.18.2 and was brought to its real-world projection so that spatial analysis could be performed. Attribute data were programmed into the computer using Git Bash to create the database, and the attribute data was carried in the PostgreSQL user interface (P.G. admin). The attribute data was hosted on a database server called Heroku so that the Spatial database could be linked with it. The spatial database was loaded into PostGIS using QGIS and was always queried on the database server. The graphics user interface and the link hosted were designed by Node.js.

Results and Discussion

Testing of Database

This test is done to decide if the connection between the geometric data about the objects and their attributes can be retrieved. This was done by designing a simple query and running the query to see if the desired result was achieved. The database was confirmed fit for analysis.

Spatial Query

Queries were put in place to retrieve information from the database. The queries implemented in this project give room to answer specific questions from the database. This was achieved due to the link between the spatial and attribute data. Furthermore, the queries were based on the products from the analysis carried out on the database.

- **Administrative login Interface**

Figure 1: The admin login interface of the database

- **Administrative Dashboard**

Figure 2: The admin dashboard of the database

- **User Login Interface**

Figure 3: The user login interface of the database

- **User information**

Figure 4: The user information in the database

Discussion

Automating the cadastral information system using open-source tools demonstrates the potential for scalable and cost-effective land administration. Compared to traditional systems, the digital approach offers real-time updates, better security, and remote access. Challenges encountered included data accuracy and server configuration, which were mitigated with proper georeferencing and cloud hosting.

Conclusion

This study developed an automated database for cadastral information using Mandate Housing Estate, Adewole, Ilorin, as a case study. A computerized cadastral information database was created to have a functioning database with PostgreSQL (PSQL) and PostGIS. A user-friendly interface was designed for the database. Different queries were deployed to check for the database's errors and efficiency, and the results were in digital format.

The database was formed using spatial and attribute data. A link was generated whereby the user and admin can log into the server to see detailed information about their Land.

Among the various results achieved is the interface where we have the user interface and the super user interface, which can also be called the admin interface. Moreover, different queries were carried out on the database to get a good working interface, which is saved and inserted in Chapter 4 (Results and Analysis).

As a result of this concluded that the Development of an automated database was successful. Furthermore, the result shows how efficiently it uses Geographic Information Systems to collect, store, analyze, and present cadastral data.

The study allowed the efficient tool to automate the cadastral database, which will be helpful for agencies such as the Office of the Surveyor General and Land Bureau to optimize land management.

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